

FORGING SINO - ECUADORIAN PROSPERITY: THE BELT AND ROAD INITIATIVE AND SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONE REVITALIZATION

Sebastián Castellano

[LinkedIn: Sebastián Gonzalo \(塞巴\) Castellano Unda](#)

Abstract

This research explores Sino - Ecuadorian commercial relations, particularly within the Belt and Road Initiative. It first traces historical and current interactions, highlighting Chinese infrastructure investments like the Coca - Codo Sinclair Dam that benefit both countries. Next, it analyzes Ecuador's Special Economic Development Zones (ZEDEs). After clarifying differences between ZEDEs, FTAs, and FTZs, the study reveals ZEDEs in Ecuador underperform relative to other Latin American countries due to regulatory and institutional issues. To tackle these problems, the research proposes reforms such as implementing a negative list model, simplifying administrative processes, and re - conceptualizing ZEDEs as Free Trade Pilot Zones, inspired by China's FTZ experience. Moreover, it identifies opportunities in the IIRSA and Belt and Road Initiative, suggesting a Manta - Manaus - Belém Free Trade Pilot Zone chain to boost regional trade. Using qualitative literature review, this study fills a knowledge gap, offering practical solutions to enhance ZEDE functionality and foster bilateral economic development.

本研究探讨了中厄之间的商业关系，尤其是在“一带一路”倡议背景下的关系。研究首先追溯了历史及当前的互动情况，着重介绍了像科卡科多 - 辛克雷大坝这样使两国都受益的中国基础设施投资项目。接下来，研究对厄瓜多尔的特殊经济开发区（ZEDEs）进行了分析。在厘清了特殊经济开发区（ZEDEs）、自由贸易区（FTA）和自由贸易园区（FTZ）之间的区别后，该研究揭示出，由于监管和制度方面的问题，厄瓜多尔的特殊经济开发区（ZEDEs）的表现相较于其他拉丁美洲国家要逊色。为了解决这些问题，本研究提出了一些改革建议，比如借鉴中国自由贸易园区的经验，实施负面清单模式、简化行政程序，以及将特殊经济开发区（ZEDEs）重新定位为自由贸易试验区。此外，研究还发现了南美洲区域基础设施一体化倡议（IIRSA）和“一带一路”倡议中蕴含的机遇，建议打造一条从曼塔到马瑙斯再到贝伦的自由贸易试验区链条，以促进区域贸易的发展。本研究采用

了定性文献综述的方法，填补了相关知识空白，为提升厄瓜多尔特殊经济开发区（ZEDEs）的功能提供了切实可行的解决方案，并推动了双边经济的发展。

Key words

Belt and Road Initiative, Special Economic Development Zones (ZEDEs), Free Trade Area (FTA), Free Trade Zone (FTZ), infrastructure investment.

Introduction

In recent years, the relationship between China and Ecuador has witnessed remarkable growth, driven by the Belt and Road Initiative. This dynamic not only has strengthened the commercial and political ties between the two countries but also has created opportunities for economic and social development. However, the operation and potential of the Special Economic Development Zones (ZEDE for its acronym in Spanish) in Ecuador, within the context of this relationship, have not been adequately explored.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the commercial relations between China and Ecuador, with an emphasis on Ecuador's participation in the Belt and Road Initiative and the Special Economic Development Zones ZEDEs. The historical and current backgrounds of these relations, the benefits and challenges that have emerged, and how the ZEDEs in Ecuador could be improved to adapt to the operation of China's Free Trade Zones and optimize the implementation of the Belt and Road Initiative will be examined.

To achieve these objectives, the qualitative method of literature review has been used. Multiple sources, including government reports, research articles, and case studies, have been reviewed to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the topics addressed.

The logical structure of this work begins with a review of the existing literature on the commercial relations between China and Latin America, with a specific focus on Ecuador. Then, the historical and current backgrounds of Ecuador's participation in the Belt and Road Initiative, as well as China's infrastructure investments in the country, are analyzed. Next, the conceptual differences between the Free Trade Area (FTA), Free Trade Zone (FTZ), and ZEDE are presented, and the characteristics and performance of the ZEDEs in Ecuador are examined. Finally, measures to improve the operation of the ZEDEs in Ecuador are proposed, based on China's experience in the Free Trade Zones.

This study aims to fill a gap in knowledge by offering a deeper understanding of the commercial relations between China and Ecuador in the context of the Belt and Road Initiative and by proposing practical solutions to improve the operation of the ZEDEs in Ecuador. Moreover, it is expected that the results of this study will contribute to the formulation of policies and business decisions that promote more sustainable and equitable economic development in both countries.

Literature Review

In this section, a brief review will be conducted on how the commercial relations between China and Latin America have been. It will also explain how the bilateral relations between China and Ecuador have been and the benefits that this diplomatic bridge has brought to both nations. It will also expound on how Ecuador joined the Belt and Road Initiative, especially how Ecuador has benefited from China's investment in the necessary infrastructure for a proper anchoring in the supply chain of the initiative. The second section is related to the Special Economic

Development Zones present in Ecuador and how China's experience in implementing these zones helps us understand the deficiencies in Ecuador and how we could correct them. Finally, a proposal for the improvement of the Special Economic Development Zones in Ecuador is presented so that they can be adapted to the operation of China's FTZs and, in this way, improve the operation of the Belt and Road Initiative. For this, the qualitative method of literature review will be used.

Background: Belt and Road Initiative in Latin America and Ecuador

In the case of Latin America, as background, we should cite one of a historical nature in the bilateral relations and another regarding the current proposal of the BRI (Belt and Road Initiative). In the first case, it can be recalled that, since the mid-16th century, Chinese ships loaded with products such as silk and porcelain crossed the Pacific Ocean bound for Acapulco, in southern Mexico. Then, part of these luxury goods from the East was transported to the port of Veracruz, and finally, from there to Europe, thus completing a true global business (Spanish. xinhuanet, 2019).

Regarding the current proposal, it should be noted that the expansion of the Belt and Road Initiative was formally carried out in 2018, with the previous fact that Sino-Latin American relations could be characterized as increasingly consolidated through five movements already deployed previously: Trade, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Finance, Cooperation, and Political Dialogue.

In that context, and mediated by the continuous deepening of bilateral relations since 2002 (Milton Reyes Herrera, 2022). China formally invited Latin America to join the initiative. However, at first, only 5 Latin American countries, including only one from South America, namely Panama, Antigua and Barbuda, Trinidad and Tobago, Guyana, and Bolivia, joined. In 2018, other South American countries such as Venezuela, Chile, and Ecuador were incorporated. As of today, in 2025, most Latin American and Caribbean countries have joined the Belt and Road Initiative. However, given the current situation of the increasingly poor international relations between the US and the rest of the world, Panama, which was one of the first participants in the Belt and Road Initiative, has taken the initiative to withdraw from the treaty under pressure from the US (Pelcastre, 2025). It is also necessary to note that Brazil and Colombia are currently in negotiations.

Formally, we can point out "five points that are presented as vital in the formal structuring of the proposal, with the aim of defining a more concrete way for its development: 1) Policy Coordination, 2) Facility Connectivity, 3) Trade, 4) Financial Integration, 5) Mobility" (Milton Reyes Herrera, 2022).

The proposal, as we can see, articulates the institutional field (policy coordination); but it also guides possibilities in the economic, cooperation, and political dialogue aspects:

- The possibility of increasing bilateral and regional trade (with the intention of practically doubling the volume of trade), and thus increasing the benefits for China and its counterparts. In this way, it is possible to create cooperation spaces to ensure supplies while strengthening political exchanges with

market-oriented national economies, especially considering the resurgent economic nationalism of some Western powers, especially the US.

- The possibility of ensuring a long-term political-economic relationship.
- The possibility of creating circumscribed spaces for the internationalization of the yuan.

Ecuador in the Belt and Road Initiative and Its Relations with China

Promoting international cooperation in productive capacity is a crucial measure for maintaining a moderate to high economic growth rate in China and advancing towards medium to high-quality levels. It is an important component for driving a new round of high-level opening up to the outside world and strengthening international competitive advantages. Moreover, it is a fundamental key for strengthening economic and trade cooperation between China and the relevant countries and deepening the construction of the Belt and Road Initiative (Guan Yuhong, 2020).

Since 2010, the presence of these companies has coincided with an increase in the presence of Chinese citizens in Ecuador. China and its companies have seriously invested in energy infrastructure projects, terrestrial connections, telecommunications, mines, and oil.

Ecuador's different development plans from 2007 to 2013 focused on intensive investment in strategic sectors lacking the necessary infrastructure. This led to a deepening of the state sector's relationship with China in terms of loans, investment, and project operation. China's presence was particularly felt in energy projects, of which 7 out of the 8 largest projects were built by companies from the People's Republic of China. Some of the most representative investments were the Coca-Codo Sinclair Hydropower Plant, La Sopladora Hydropower Plant, and the San Francisco Hydropower Dam. It can be said, then, that the start of inter-institutional and governmental cooperation relations for development regularly began in 2009 when the contract for the construction of Coca-Codo Sinclair was signed (Milton Reyes Herrera, 2022).

The flagship projects resulting from Sino-Ecuadorian relations are as follows:

Table 1: Proyectos más destacados de la cooperación sino-ecuatorianas

Date	Project Name	Amount Invested	Type of Project
October, 2009	Coca-Codo Sinclair Hydroelectric Dam	\$1.98 USD billions	Energy
October, 2010	Sopladora Hydroelectric Dam	\$672 USD millions	Energy
August, 2011	Villonaco wind farm Project	\$34.5 USD millions	Renewable Energies
April, 2013	San Francisco Hydroelectric Dam	\$312 USD millions	Energy
October, 2014	Coca Codo Sinclair transmission system	\$509 USD millions	Energy
February, 2016	Complejo Educativo Yachay	\$198 USD millions	Education

December, 2018	Infrastructure and Reconstruction	\$69 USD millions	Others
----------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------	--------

Source: (Milton Reyes Herrera, 2022) (Banco Central del Ecuador)

Ecuador has records of several Chinese companies that participated in these projects, including **Sinohydro**-Coca-Codo Sinclear Hydroelectric Dam, **Gezhouba**-Sopladora Hydroelectric Dam and Flood Control Project Bulubulo, **Harbin**-Hydroelectric Dam Minas San Francismoa and Transmission System 500kv, **CNEEC**-Mazad Dudas Project and Hydroelectric Dam Quijos, **Hydrochina**- Hydroelectric Dam Delsitanisagua, **CRCC Ton Guang Investment**-Mirador Project (copper), **Goldwind**- Villonaco wind farm Poject

The first antecedent towards the Belt and Road Initiative was the participation of Ecuadorian state institutions, such as the Central Bank of Ecuador, together with delegations from the Ministry of Economy and Finance and the Ministry of Transportation and Public Works, in the International Financial Seminar on Exchange and Cooperation of the Belt and Road, held in Beijing and Shanghai from November 15 to 22, 2017. It was reported that this participation would be relevant for Ecuador, given that "the axis of the planned conversations and exhibitions revolves around increasing the interrelation and generating new cooperation opportunities between China and Latin America"... (through) "the coordination of policies and the integration of the physical infrastructures of the countries", all of which could help "reduce the costs of productive inputs and alleviate logistical obstacles, boosting productivity and faster global growth" (BCE, 2017).

As already mentioned, Ecuador showed interest in associating with the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), being the fourth country in South America to adhere to the initiative in December 2018. Subsequently, Ecuador joined the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB), becoming the first Latin American country to be part of this financial entity as of November 2019 (Xinhua, 2019).

According to the same source, Manta has all the potential "to become the gateway for all of Asia-Pacific, including Australia, to South America for people and goods... (and)... to boost tourism, business, and trade with Singapore, China, Japan, among others" (Xinhua, 2019), something that can also be found in proposals such as the South American Regional Infrastructure Integration Initiative (IIRSA), and in the possibility of linking the Ecuadorian and Brazilian Amazon regions (Herrera M. A., 2016). That is to say, the proposal to use the port of Manabí in Ecuador is not new.

The IIRSA, therefore, is an initiative of the Latin American countries to integrate among themselves. Thus, it represents a theoretical basis with solid practical applications that could perfectly fit into the logic of the Belt and Road Initiative. Its objective is: To connect by land the port of Manta, located in the province of Manabí on the Ecuadorian Pacific coast, with the port of Francisco de Orellana (El Coca), located in the province of Orellana in the Ecuadorian Amazon, following by river along the Napo River until reaching the Amazon River in Iquitos (Peru), continuing along this river until reaching Tabatinga (Brazil), to flow into the Free Trade Zone of Manaus and finally to Belém in Brazil (Herrera M. A., 2016) (Appendix 1).

In the original project, the commercial potential in Manaus was considered, with the possibility of strengthening the industrial hub of this city in Brazil (fed by the region's production) and as a core of bioceanic manufacturing and trade. However, while this may be interesting, the proposal, when deployed with integrated initiatives towards a Manta-Manaus-Belém continuity, expands the portfolio of opportunities and initiatives (Appendix 2).

Characteristics of FTZs/ZEDs in Ecuador

The first characteristic to highlight is the conceptual differences between the Free Trade Area (FTA), Free Trade Zone (FTZ), and Special Economic Development Zone (ZEDE for its acronym in Spanish).

A Free Trade Area 自由贸易区 can be understood as the elimination of tariffs and other restrictive trade regulations between two or more independent customs entities with the aim of trade liberalization. These customs entities are sovereign states, and the objective is commercial opening and the elimination of tariff barriers among the members of the trade area, while maintaining independent external trade policies and it is achieved through bilateral agreements (Fuhua, 2025).

Free Trade Zone 自由贸易园区 refers to a specific small area within a certain country or region where preferential tax policies and special regulatory policies are applied. It is a trading market established within the country itself in accordance with the laws and regulations of the country (or region). In this part of the territory, any imported goods are considered to be outside the customs border in terms of import tariffs and other taxes such as income tax, and are exempt from the application of the normal customs control regime (Fuhua, 2025).

A Special Economic Development Zone (ZEDE for its acronym in Spanish) It is a concept given in the Organic Code of Production, Trade, and Investments (COPCI) of Ecuador, where it is stated that "A 'Zona Franca' shall be understood as the geographical area delimited within the national territory which, for the purposes of this law, is subject to special regimes determined in matters of foreign trade, customs, taxation, financial, agro-industrial, technological, and capital treatment, in which industrial activities of goods, services, commercial activities, among others, are developed."

The first ZEDE established in Ecuador was the Esmeraldas 'Zona Franca', whose strict English translation is "Free Zone." In terms of functions, the closest translation into Chinese is "自由贸易园区," that is, an FTZ. By transitivity and functions, we can say that the closest concept to a ZEDE in Ecuador is the FTZ or 自由贸易园区. The reader should also understand that the concept of FTA does not exist in Ecuador, which already generates the first limitation on the customs union in a Free Trade Area between two countries (Appendix 3).

The second characteristic is the presence of the so-called Positive List 正面清单 which occurs when the host country makes a partial opening and specifically lists

the activities or companies that are allowed access to the market, either for local or foreign investors. Within the Organic Code of Production, Trade, and Investments (COPCI), the concept of "Positive List" does not exist. However, it follows exactly the same concept, and these allowed activities are: Industrial activities of goods, Industrial activities of services, and Commercial and Logistics activities (ECIJA GPA, 2024).

The third characteristic, following the argumentative thread of the paragraph, is that the objectives of the ZEDEs in Ecuador are basically two. The first is the attraction of investments, and its difficulty, as mentioned, is the existence of the positive list that limits the activities in which one can invest. The second objective is the continuation of the import substitution industrialization project because, in fact, what was originally intended with the creation of these free zones was the attraction of capital that would contribute to manufacturing and improve goods with added value. This situation will be taken up later with a proposal (Appendix 4).

All these characteristics, including the previously mentioned conceptual differences, have led to a disappointing result compared to the rest of the Latin American regions. Currently, there are 9 ZEDEs in Ecuador as follows:

Graphic 1 : Special Economic Development Zone in Ecuador

Source: (Ministerio de Producción, Comercio Exterior, Inversiones y Pesca , 2023)
Translated by: Sebastián Castellano

These ZEDs have generated profits and employment, but compared to other Latin American countries, it has been quite low. In this regard, the Association of Free Zones of the Americas (2023) indicates that as of 2022, the ZEDs in Ecuador generated 3,364 direct jobs, while in other Latin American countries, these figures are higher. For example, in countries like Panama and Colombia, 26,889 and 147,000 jobs were created, respectively. Also, the ZEDs have attracted an investment of \$1.212 billion for Ecuador, unlike neighboring countries such as Brazil (\$7.011 billion) and Colombia (\$11.489 billion) (AZFA, 2024).

Prospects and Opportunities for Integration into the Belt and Road Initiative through Free Trade Pilot Zone

As described in the first part of this text, the IIRSA originally proposed the possibility of including Manta, Ecuador as a port for the passage of goods at the Latin American level, where the purpose is to link Manta with the Manaus, Brazil Free Trade Zone and then with Belém, Brazil. This same route, Reyes (2022) has proposed as the best option to also link with the Belt and Road Initiative. Of course, each country has its own regulations regarding imports and tariffs. However, Brazil already has an advantage with the port of Manaus being a free trade zone, and according to BioEconomía (2023), since 2023, there has been a plan to make Belém also a free trade zone.

This means that the IIRSA initiative and the opportunities presented by the Belt and Road Initiative for the passage of goods through Latin America would be even more benefited by the creation of a chain of Free Trade Pilot Zones along all the land and river routes involving the Manta-Manaus-Belém trajectory. Given that this study focuses on the Ecuadorian case and its connection to the Belt and Road Initiative, it should start with a proposal for structural changes that Ecuador needs regarding the operation of the Free Trade Zones or ZEDs. As well as thinking about the opening of a new Free Trade Pilot Zone in Manta.

It should be noted that this is not the first time a Free Trade Zone has been proposed in Manta. There were two Free Trade Zone projects, which were managed by ZOFRAMA S.A. and ZONA MANTA S.A. However, according to Melvyn Castro (2023), that projects failed to attract the expected investments or generate the expected employment. Among other reasons, there were regulatory problems, lack of clarity in the processes, shortage of infrastructure, lack of institutional coordination, and insufficient political support. Therefore, it is urgent to solve the structural problems that the economic development zones have faced in the past and at present. These solutions should be based on the following:

1. Creation of negative lists 负面清单模式: The Ecuadorian government or relevant competent entities should present a list of sectors or activities to which restrictions are applied or in which the participation of foreign investors is not allowed, or in some cases, even local investors. Everything that is not on the negative list is automatically permitted for investment and operation in the market. Full access is granted under more favorable conditions than the national treatment or the Most Favored Nation treatment.

2. Simplify the verification systems and registration systems, and implement a subscribed capital system with corresponding penalties for false declaration of capital and capital flight, as well as supervision before and after investment.
3. Reconceptualize what is understood as "Free Zones" or ZEDs, because these currently only focus on attracting investments and promoting the manufacturing of products with added value. Instead, the creation of a Free Trade Pilot Zone should be a priority, as this is a breakthrough point and a testing ground for experimenting with the liberalization and facilitation of investments in China. In addition, it provides an institutional foundation for development, participation, and leadership in the formulation of international free trade rules.
4. Regarding the characteristics of Free Trade Pilot Zones 自贸试验区, there are certain beneficial features that Ecuador could adopt, regardless of its economic system:
 - a. Platforms for experimenting with new international economic and trade rules.
 - b. Spaces for coordinated regional economic development.
 - c. A clear framework that keeps risks under control.
 - d. Accelerated pathways to adapt to high-standard international trade norms.
 - e. Institutional innovation as the central element, instead of political advantages.
 - f. Test grounds for reform and opening up—not just enhanced development zones.
 - g. Implementation of a customs model of “outside the customs border within the territory” (境内关外).
 - h. A balanced interaction between state guidance and market mechanisms.
 - i. Activation of market players’ vitality and entrepreneurial dynamism.
 - j. Nurturing grounds for new business formats and commercial models.
 - k. Drivers for upgrading and modernizing industrial chains.
 - l. Engines to discover new sources of economic growth.
 - m. Strategic nodes for aligning policies, infrastructure, and trade under the BRI framework.
 - n. Magnet zones for attracting talent, investment, and financial innovation.
 - o. Pilot settings for testing financial tools like cross-border currency settlement.

- p. Catalysts for digital economy development and cross-border data flows.
- q. Laboratories for post-border reforms, especially in investment and intellectual property.
- r. Platforms that help align domestic standards with international frameworks such as RCEP and CPTPP.
- s. Safe spaces to trial industrial openness in a controlled environment.
- t. Focal points for advanced industries and regional productive integration.
- u. Connectors that link R&D and design with downstream manufacturing.
- v. Foundations for building international logistics and connectivity hubs.
- w. Bridges for cultural exchange and strengthened international cooperation.

Another characteristic that should be separately mentioned is that Free Trade Pilot Zones are used as service platforms for the construction of the Belt and Road Initiative. Strengthening productive capacity cooperation with China serves the interests of both parties. On the one hand, Chinese companies have sufficient funds, advanced technology, and strong construction capabilities, as well as extensive experience in the management and operation of infrastructure areas such as electricity, roads, and telecommunications. This enables them to meet Ecuador's needs to accelerate the development of its infrastructure and, at the same time, helps expand the size of the international market for the Chinese infrastructure sector. On the other hand, Ecuador has abundant resources in the form of raw materials for food production, mineral resources, and hydrocarbons. The cooperation between the two parties can not only transform Ecuador's competitive advantage in raw materials into an economic development opportunity but also increase the diversification of China's resource imports.

As mentioned in the first chapter, China and its companies have already invested in strategic sectors, including in the Yachay technological ZEDE. It is also important to highlight another type of social-level investment. For example, the construction of the IESS Quito Sur Hospital and the Hospital de Los Ceibos in Guayaquil are examples of the positive impact of Sino-Ecuadorian cooperation on urban and social development. Another significant project was the renovation and expansion of the Monte Sinaí Road in Guayaquil. In addition, in 2023, in the town of Guano, Chimborazo province, houses financed by Chinese institutions were handed over to 144 people living in extreme poverty and with some type of disability, as part of the corporate social responsibility programs of Chinese-funded companies.

All these investments, both in infrastructure and in diplomacy, have made it possible for a complete integration between Ecuador and China. Each side takes advantage of its respective comparative advantages, and Ecuador serves as an anchor point in the Belt and Road Initiative through the port of Manta as a Free Trade Zone.

Appendix

- (1) Regarding the Pacific connection, linked to the geographical area of Manta, there would be an articulation with an area that would be composed of the autonomous regions or planning zones: 4 (Province of Manabí, Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas), 3 (especially, the provinces of Tungurahua and Cotopaxi), tangentially the 9 (Quito Metropolitan District) and the 2 (provinces of Napo and Orellana) on the Ecuadorian side; while, in the Brazilian Northeast region and the Atlantic connection, it would be linked with the Brazilian territorial organization, specifically with region 2 (Northeast Region), where the states of Maranhão, Piauí, Ceará, Rio Grande do Norte, Paraíba, Pernambuco, Alagoas, Sergipe, and Bahia are located (Durán, 2011).
- (2) At this point, it is important to note that the IIRSA (South American Regional Infrastructure Integration Initiative), guided by the coordination of intergovernmental actions of the twelve South American countries with the vision of building a common agenda to drive infrastructure integration projects in transportation, energy, and communications (IIRSA, 2015) was related to the COSIPLAN (South American Infrastructure and Planning Council), composed of the ministers of the infrastructure and/or planning areas or their equivalents designated by the Member States of UNASUR (Union of South American Nations) (IIRSA, 2015). Based on this, until 2017, the year when UNASUR was still fully operational, some general guidelines had been established and preliminary results had been outlined.
- (3) Continuing from the above, the first ZEDE (Special Economic Development Zone) was created in Esmeraldas in 1985, which certainly led to the need for legislation to regulate the authorization, creation, and operation of the Free Trade Zones (FTZs) in the country (Ortiz, 2023). Because of this, and rather late compared to the rest of the region, it was only in 1991 that the Law came into force under which 14 Free Trade Zones (FTZs) were established throughout the Ecuadorian territory; but not all of them thrived. In 2010, the Organic Code of Production, Trade, and Investments came into force, which repealed the old Free Trade Zone Law of 1991 and led to the creation of the ZEDE concept. However, before delving further into this, it is important to note that currently, three of the fourteen free zones established under the old regulation are still in effect, according to the Ministry of Production, Foreign Trade, Investments, and Fisheries.
- (4) A third characteristic is the way in which companies are authorized to operate within the ZEDE according to the Organic Code of Production, Trade, and Investments (2010), which, as already explained, introduced the ZEDes into Ecuadorian legislation. The establishment of a ZEDE must be carried out through a request from public sector institutions or Decentralized Autonomous Governments. After analyzing the convenience of its authorization, and if it is deemed convenient, the corresponding zone is constituted by a resolution issued by the Sectoral Production Council; whose approval will be valid for a minimum period of 20 years. Similarly, the National Free Zones Council is responsible for qualifying the administrators and operators of the ZEDes; that is, in principle, the procedures to obtain the

operating authorization are: submit the request through a public initiative, issue the declaration of the ZEDE, and receive the authorization of the administrators and the corresponding qualification of the operators (COPCI).

Posface

One topic that was not explored in depth is the strategic use of Ecuador's comparative advantages in raw material production, especially in agriculture. As mentioned in the Literature Review, one of the objectives of ZEDEs is to promote import substitution (or more recently, the substitution of exports for higher value-added products). However, this approach may cause the country to lose sight of the products it is best at producing due to its natural wealth, a common trait among Latin American countries.

For this reason, the proposal can be expanded further by analyzing which economic activities Ecuador should focus on based on its comparative advantages. Therefore, future studies should include competitiveness or comparative advantage indexes and assess which products Ecuador can truly specialize in, both in comparison to China and to the rest of the world.

Conclusions

1. Trade relations between China and Ecuador have a long history, with roots going back to colonial times. Today, the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has significantly boosted these ties. Ecuador has joined the initiative and received substantial Chinese investment in infrastructure, especially in the energy sector. Projects such as the Coca-Codo Sinclair and Sopladora hydroelectric plants are clear examples of this cooperation.
2. This cooperation has been mutually beneficial. China has expanded its presence in Latin America and diversified its sources of resources, while Ecuador has improved its infrastructure and promoted economic development. Moreover, investments in social sectors, such as hospital and housing construction, have had a positive impact on the Ecuadorian population.
3. ZEDEs in Ecuador have underperformed compared to those in other Latin American countries. They have generated less employment and attracted fewer investments than countries such as Panama, Colombia, and Brazil. This is partly due to regulatory issues, lack of institutional coordination, and a narrowly focused approach on investment attraction and manufacturing promotion.

4. It is necessary to reform the functioning of ZEDEs in Ecuador. Proposals such as creating negative lists, simplifying verification and registration systems, and rethinking ZEDEs as Experimental Free Trade Zones can help address these issues. These reforms are based on China's experience with Free Trade Zones and could improve ZEDE competitiveness in Ecuador.
5. The South American Regional Infrastructure Integration Initiative (IIRSA) and the Belt and Road Initiative offer a great opportunity for Ecuador. The creation of a chain of Experimental Free Trade Zones along the Manta–Manaus–Belém route could increase regional trade and strengthen Latin American economic integration.
6. Continued cooperation with China in productive capacity is beneficial for both countries. China can continue investing in infrastructure in Ecuador, while Ecuador can supply natural resources to China. Furthermore, cooperation in social and urban development areas can continue to improve the quality of life for the Ecuadorian population.

Research achievements

A comparative analysis of the concepts and operations of Free Trade Area (FTA), Free Trade Zone (FTZ), and ZEDE was conducted, helping to clarify the differences and similarities between these trade models. Additionally, a comparative analysis of ZEDE performance in Ecuador versus other Latin American countries was carried out, identifying key areas for improvement.

Based on the analysis of the collected information, proposals were formulated to improve the operation of ZEDEs in Ecuador. These proposals, inspired by China's experience with Free Trade Zones, address regulatory aspects, administrative simplification, and a reconceptualization of ZEDEs.

Opportunities for Ecuador's economic development were identified within the context of the Belt and Road Initiative, particularly regarding the creation of a chain of Experimental Free Trade Zones along the Manta–Manaus–Belém corridor.

The information gathered and analyzed was synthesized into a document presenting a clear and concise overview of trade relations between China and Ecuador, as well as future cooperation prospects between the two countries. This document can serve as an educational resource for students and professionals interested in international trade relations and Latin America's economic development.

References

- Spanish. xinhuanet. (25 de 10 de 2019). *XINHUA ESPAÑOL*. Obtenido de https://spanish.xinhuanet.com/2019-10/25/c_138502757.htm
- AZFA. (2024). *Asociación de Zonas Francas de las Américas*. Obtenido de <https://asociacionzonasfrancas.org/es/informacion/noticias>

- Banco Central del Ecuador. (Reportada en la Balanza de Pagos - Boletín No 89). *Banco Central del Ecuador*. Obtenido de <https://contenido.bce.fin.ec/documentos/Estadisticas/SectorExterno/BalanzaPagos/InversionExtranjera/Directa/indice.htm>
- BCE. (2017). *Seminario Internacional "La Franja y La Ruta" en China. 17-11-2017*. Obtenido de <https://www.bce.fin.ec/index.php/boletines-de-prensa-archivo/item/1016>
- BioEconomía.info. (18 de 10 de 2023). <https://www.bioeconomia.info/2023/10/18/proponen-crear-en-el-norte-de-brasil-una-zona-franca-bioeconomica/>. Obtenido de <https://www.bioeconomia.info/2023/10/18/proponen-crear-en-el-norte-de-brasil-una-zona-franca-bioeconomica/>
- Castro, M. O. (12 de 06 de 2023). *REVISTA DE MANABÍ*. Obtenido de <https://revistademanabi.com/2023/06/12/sobre-zonas-francas/>
- COPCI. (s.f.). CÓDIGO ORGÁNICO DE LA PRODUCCIÓN, COMERCIO E INVERSIONES. Ecuador: <https://www.aduana.gob.ec/la-institucion/codigo-organico-copci/>.
- Durán, S. (2011). Brasil en el contexto de la Iniciativa para la Integración de la Infraestructura Regional Sudamericana (IIRSA) y el corredor multimodal Manta-Manaos, periodo 2003-2010. 1-80.
- ECIJA GPA. (2024). *ZONAS FRANCAS EN ECUADOR: NAVEGANDO EL NUEVO RÉGIMEN LEGAL*. Obtenido de <https://www.ecija.com>
- Fuhua, D. (2025). 自由贸易试验区概述, Presentation at 自由贸易试验区课, at the SWUFE. Chengdu, Sichuan, China.
- Guan Yuhong, G. G. (2020). “一带一路”倡议下中国—亚美尼亚产能合作研究. *China Academic Journal Electronic Publishing House*, 11-35.
- Herrera, M. A. (2016). La Conexión Interoceánica Manta – Manaos- Belem: Oportunidad para la Integración; Proyección Económica, Política y de Seguridad Sudamericana. *Anais do 2º CONGEO- Congresso Brasileiro de Geografia Política, Geopolítica e Gestão do Território Natal, Rio Grande do Norte*, 1448-1470.
- IIRSA. (15 de 04 de 2015). *COSIPLAN*. Obtenido de chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.iirsa.org/admin_iirsa_web/Uploads/Documents/cartera_montevideo15_Caracterizacion_SEA_%20Ejes_AMA_AND_CAP_HPP_MCC_anexo6.pdf
- Milton Reyes Herrera, J. M. (2022). *Historia de la Migración China en Ecuador, Entre la Diáspora y el Desarrollo de la Franja y la Ruta*. Quito: Alectrión.
- Ministerio de Producción, Comercio Exterior, Inversiones y Pesca . (2023). Obtenido de <http://www.inteligenciaproductiva.gob.ec/zonas-especiales-de-desarrollo-economico>
- Ortiz, H. (18 de 10 de 2023). Nuevas zonas francas. *El Universo*, págs. <https://www.eluniverso.com/opinion/columnistas/nuevas-zonas-francas-nota/>.

Pelcastre, J. (11 de 03 de 2025). *Dialogo Américas*. Obtenido de <https://dialogo-americas.com/es/articles/panama-rompe-con-la-iniciativa-de-la-franja-y-la-ruta-de-china/>

Xinhua. (08 de 04 de 2019). *América Economía*. Obtenido de Las obras que China impulsará en Ecuador: <https://www.americaeconomia.com/las-obras-que-china-impulsara-en-ecuador>